

TNL-SPH: Open-source modular SPH solver for modern computing platforms based on GPU accelerators

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Abstract

TNL-SPH is a novel open-source implementation of Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH), integrated as a sub-module of the Template Numerical Library (TNL), designed for modern distributed computing platforms with GPU accelerators. Focusing on hydrodynamic problems using weakly compressible formulations, TNL-SPH offers a modular, high-performance framework for implementing various SPH schemes and particle methods. Developed in C++17, it leverages TNL's templated vectors and expression templates to provide compact, algebraic representations of numerical schemes, simplifying the development of complex physical models. Its multilayered design separates parallelism, performance, and numerical methods, enabling seamless execution across diverse hardware, including multi-GPU and distributed systems. TNL-SPH outperforms existing SPH codes for free-surface flows and supports scalable, high-performance simulations. This paper presents the design, implementation, and performance of TNL-SPH, alongside its applications in hydraulic problems, demonstrating its versatility and efficiency for scientific and engineering computations.

PROGRAM SUMMARY

Program Title: TNL-SPH

CPC Library link to program files: (to be added by Technical Editor)

Developer's repository link: <https://gitlab.com/tnl-project/tnl-sph>

Licensing provisions (please choose one): MIT

Programming language: C++, Python

Nature of problem (approx. 50-250 words): Particle methods are a family of numerical algorithms in which point-like objects (particles) interact pairwise and evolve based on those interactions [1, 2]. We focus on the high-performance implementation of the particle methods, primarily targeting GPU accelerators. Building on general particle concepts, we utilize particles to solve hydraulic problems involving free surface flow using the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method.

Solution method (approx. 50-250 words): We propose an implementation based on a Unifying definition of the particle method [1]. By building on the Template Numerical Library (TNL) and utilizing template metaprogramming, the framework enables a single code to run efficiently across diverse hardware architectures. TNL's expression templates provide a simple and compact approach to implementing numerical schemes, ensuring a clear correspondence between the algebraic form of the equations and the resulting code.

Additional comments including restrictions and unusual features (approx. 50-250 words): TNL-SPH provides a general framework for implementing short-range interaction particle methods. The SPH solver within this framework offers multiple formulations of the method – δ -WCSPH, RSPH, and SHTC-SPH schemes, along with various boundary conditions for solid walls, including also open boundaries. The code supports multi-GPU computing and, for hydrodynamic problems, it surpasses the performance of other available SPH codes.

References

- [1] J. Pahlke and I. F. Sbalzarini. A unifying mathematical definition of particle methods. *IEEE Open Journal of the Computer Society*, 4:97–108, 2023.
- [2] J. Pahlke and I. F. Sbalzarini. On the computational power of particle methods, 2023.

Keywords: particle methods, SPH, GPU programming, free surface flows

1. Introduction

We introduce TNL-SPH, a novel open-source Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) implementation, designed for modern distributed computing platforms with GPU accelerators. TNL-SPH mainly focuses on hydrodynamic problems using weakly compressible formulations. Its modular and general design facilitates a straightforward implementation of various SPH schemes and other particle methods. TNL-SPH is developed as a submodule of the Template Numerical Library (TNL) [38, 28], an open-source C++ library created at CTU in Prague, which aims to simplify the development of high-performance numerical codes for modern parallel architectures, particularly GPUs. Like TNL, TNL-SPH is implemented in C++ (C++17) using modern programming paradigms. The code is available at <https://gitlab.com/tnl-project/tnl-sph>. TNL-SPH is single code running across different hardware, supports multi-GPU and distributed computations, and provides advanced SPH schemes.

Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH), a fully Lagrangian mesh-free method, has gained significant popularity for modeling fluid flows, free-surface dynamics, and multiphase systems. Originally developed for astrophysics [16, 32] to simulate large-scale cosmological phenomena, SPH has since been widely adopted in engineering, geophysics, high-energy physics, and computer graphics. Its ability to handle complex geometries, discontinuities, and free surfaces makes it particularly suitable for scenarios where grid-based methods are less effective. As SPH techniques have evolved, numerous specialized implementations have emerged, each tailored to specific domains or computational strategies.

Numerous SPH codes have been developed to meet the needs of various scientific communities. Thanks to the efforts of SPHERIC [46], most SPH implementations, including both open-source and commercial codes, are cataloged on the SPHERIC website. In the engineering and fluid dynamics communities, tools such as GPUSPH [21], DualSPHysics [13], and AQUAgpusph [7] provide frameworks for free-surface flow simulations, using GPU acceleration. GPU accelerated SPH schemes for fluid flows provide also codes SPHinXsys [55] and SPLisHSPlasH [3]. In astrophysics, codes such as Gadget-2 [47], ChaNGa [24], SPHYNX [4], Phantom [43], and Shamrock [12] have been extensively used for galaxy formation, star cluster evolution, and accretion disk dynamics. In recent years, SPH-EXA [5] has been developed to achieve high-performance, exascale, multiplatform SPH applications, with its cornerstone library [25] supporting efficient neighbor search and particle distribution. In addition, frameworks for general particle methods and algorithms provide distributed particle representations and neighbor search techniques. OpenPPM [44] is an efficient parallel particle-mesh library for scalable particles system simulations. Its successor, OpenFPM [22], is an open-source C++ framework for high-performance particle and hybrid simulations on CPUs and GPUs.

With numerous particle-based frameworks available, one might question the need for another SPH code. TNL-SPH targets hydraulic applications, leveraging the general properties of particle methods as a computational algorithm while providing a high-level, user-friendly abstraction. TNL-SPH currently slightly outperforms existing SPH codes for free-surface flows and supports multi-GPU computing with effective scaling. Unlike most SPH codes, TNL-SPH adopts a multilayered design that distinctly separates parallelism, performance, and numerical methods. This structure enables seamless utilization across various computing platforms. We provide a general framework for point cloud data or particle representation, which can be adapted to implement diverse particle methods and algorithms. Our approach aligns with the *Unifying Mathematical Definition of Particle Method* proposed by Pahlke [40], demonstrating the versatility of computational particle methods [41, 39]. By utilizing TNL's templated vectors and expression templates, numerical schemes can be written in compact vector forms that directly correspond to their algebraic representations, simplifying and accelerating the implementation of physical models and numerical methods. TNL-SPH is designed to allow easy access to and extension of the main simulation time loop, a key feature for developing complex and specialized applications. As a header-only library, TNL-SPH requires no separate compilation except for the included example programs.

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This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we describe our design choices and provide a technical overview of our implementation of the general particle structure and neighbor search algorithms. Next, we detail the implementation of the SPH solver and list the numerical schemes and features included. Benchmarks and performance results are presented in Section 3. Finally, in Section 3.2, we explain how to use TNL-SPH to solve hydraulic problems or develop specific applications.

2. TNL-SPH design and features

The following sections describe the implementation details of the proposed particle data structure, neighbor search algorithms, and design of the particle solver, implementing the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method. The implementation is designed to meet the following requirements, which we believe are not fully addressed by existing codes:

- Clear separation between performance-related and numerical code.
- SPH and other numerical methods implementation must be free of hardware- or architecture-specific code.
- The particle structure must support the implementation of other *short-range interaction* particle methods.
- The neighbor search interface must be unified, allowing the neighbor search algorithm to be changed without modifying other parts of the code. Assuming multiple particle sets, the neighbor search must be capable of searching each particle set independently.
- The main time loops of the simulation must be accessible and extensible, enabling user-defined functions to be inserted between any two operations.

To meet these requirements, our implementation leverages the shared properties of various particle methods. Heuristically spoken, by particle method we mean set of particles, where each particle i is point in space \mathbf{x}_i with associated properties ω_i and these particles interact by mutually independent interactions, typically limited to closed particle neighborhood

$$\frac{d\mathbf{x}_i}{dt} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} \mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j, \omega_i, \omega_j), \quad \frac{d\omega_i}{dt} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} \mathbf{f}_{\omega}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j, \omega_i, \omega_j) \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{f}_{\mathbf{x}}$ and \mathbf{f}_{ω} represent the interaction function. Following the proper mathematical definition by Pahlke [40], a particle method algorithm is defined as a 7-tuple $(P, G, u, f, i, e, \dot{e})$ consisting of two data structures:

$$\begin{aligned} P &:= A_1 \times A_2 \times \dots \times A_n && \text{the particle space,} \\ G &:= B_1 \times B_2 \times \dots \times B_m && \text{the global variable space} \end{aligned}$$

such that $[G \times P^*]$ represents the state space of the particle methods, along with five functions

$$\begin{aligned} u &:= [G \times P^*] \times \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^* && \text{the neighborhood function,} \\ f &:= G \rightarrow \{\top, \perp\} && \text{the stopping condition,} \\ i &:= G \times P \times P \rightarrow P \times P && \text{the interact function,} \\ e &:= G \times P \rightarrow G \times P^* && \text{the evolve function,} \\ \dot{e} &:= G \rightarrow G && \text{the evolve function of global variables.} \end{aligned}$$

Each A_i represents a property of a particle (e.g., position, velocity, mass), each B_i represents a global variable (e.g., time step, viscosity, external force), and the asterisk in P^* denotes the *Kleene star*. Pahlke [40] proved that this algorithm is Turing complete and satisfies the parallelization theorem. This proof was later extended to distributed-memory computer systems [41], which also demonstrated the computational power of particle methods [39].

The unifying particle method algorithm outlines our implementation. We provide a framework where various particle methods can be implemented by specifying two data structures and four functions (*stopping condition, interaction function, and evolution functions for points and properties*). The fifth function, the neighbor search function,

provides core routine that cannot be defined as simply in practice, as it requires more than a few lines of code. Custom neighbor search algorithms can be implemented, but they demand additional effort. To identify neighboring particles, we provide implementations of the Cell List (CL) and Cell List with Explicitly Stored Neighbors (CLWL) algorithms.

The TNL-SPH framework adopts a modular design, organized into four layers, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the TNL-SPH four-layer abstraction.

The first layer consists of the Template Numerical Library (TNL), which handles parallelism and architecture-dependent code. The second layer implements the data structure for particles as part of the TNL. The third layer is core of the TNL-SPH submodule and connects the particle data structure to the numerical models and their variables, managing simulation control and I/O operations. The fourth layer implements the numerical models and schemes as part of the TNL-SPH submodule. In the following subsections, we provide details of the individual layers.

2.1. Layer 1: Architecture dependent structures

The architecture dependent primitives (such as memory management and parallel algorithms) are implemented by the Template Numerical Library (TNL) [38], independently of the actual numerical code. TNL currently supports multicore CPUs, GPUs both by NVIDIA and AMD and distributed systems, all managed via unified interface. This allows to single code to run on different platforms without any changes. To distinguish between different architectures, each data structure requiring dynamic memory allocation or parallel algorithms specifies its device using a template parameter `Device`. TNL provides skeletons or patterns for parallel algorithms, combining them with user-defined C++ lambda functions. Implementing these lambda functions, which define the content of parallel operations, is significantly simpler than writing platform-specific code, especially GPU kernels.

Another key TNL concept heavily used in our application are *expression templates*. For example, consider the expression $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{a} + 2\mathbf{b} + 3\mathbf{c}$ where vectors $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}$ are allocated on a GPU and contain 3-dimensional static vectors (e.g., \mathbf{x} represents 3D coordinates of particles). This can be written directly in code as `x = a + 2 * b + 3 * c;`. The compiler transforms this into a single GPU kernel using lazy evaluation, significantly simplifying the implementation of numerical algorithms, such as time integration schemes.

To further simplify numerical code implementation, TNL provides additional data structures alongside parallel algorithms, including multidimensional arrays with flexible indexing, matrices (including sparse matrices), regular grids, and unstructured meshes [28].

2.2. Layer 2: Particles data structure

In addition to TNL's existing data structures, we implement a general particle data structure that provides neighbor search algorithms and tools for working with arbitrarily distributed points. This particle structure includes functions to iterate over particles and their neighbors within a cutoff radius r_c . As an argument, the neighbors loop takes a lambda

function specifying the inter-particle interactions. The design based on lambda functions is inherent to the whole library, and the particle structure aligns with other parallel tools. Features such as domain decomposition and selection of particles in specific spatial subdomains are implemented, enabling distributed and multi-GPU computations, being also useful for some of the SPH algorithms such as multiresolution. The particle structure is analogous to data structures for unstructured meshes in mesh-based methods [28], providing the basic building block supporting a wide range of numerical methods.

The particle structure implementation consists of a base class `ParticlesBase`, from which we derive particle systems with specific neighbor search algorithms. Currently, we provide classes `class ParticlesCellList` implementing *cell list* (CL) and `class ParticlesCellListWithList` implementing *cell list with explicitly stored neighbors – cell list with list* (CLWL) (also known as *Verlet list* (VL)), which explicitly stores the neighbors.

2.2.1. Particles representation

To describe the particle class implementation, consider n dimensional domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, with set of N continuously labeled unstructured points (nodes, particles) $\mathcal{X} = \{\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_N : \mathbf{x}_i \in \overline{\Omega}\}$, where $\overline{\Omega} = \Omega \cup \partial\Omega$. By *particle system* we understand the ordered set of corresponding particle indices $\mathcal{P} = \{i : \mathbf{x}_i \in \mathcal{X}\}$. For every particle $i \in \mathcal{P}$ its *particle neighborhood* is defined as set $\mathcal{N}_i = \{j \in \mathcal{P} : \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\|_2 < r_{cut,i}\}$, characterized by *cutoff radius* $r_{cut,i}$ (sometimes also called *stencil size* or *search radius*). The number of points in the neighborhood \mathcal{N}_i of point $i \in \mathcal{P}$ is denoted by $N_i = |\mathcal{N}_i|$.

The particles base class `ParticleBase` contains coordinates of individual points $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^n$, which are stored using `TNL::Containers::StaticVector<dim, RealType>` with `RealType` corresponds to `float` or `double` based on user preferences. The vector \mathbf{x} of all N points is stored as continuous memory chunk using `TNL::Containers::Array<PointType, Device, IndexType>`, where `PointType` represents type alias for `TNL::Containers::StaticVector<dim, RealType>`. This vector is allocated with size $N_{alloc} \geq N$, where N tracks the number of active particles, avoiding frequent reallocations in computations with a growing number of points. The spatial domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ occupied by particles is represented by an implicit uniform Cartesian grid $\mathcal{G}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{G},0}, N_{\mathcal{G},dim}, r_c)$, where $\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{G},0}$ represents origin of the grid, $N_{\mathcal{G},dim}$ are its dimensions and r_c is the uniform cell edge length, equal to the cutoff radius.

Since all search implementations use some variant of a sorting algorithm, the particles base includes an array of permutations $\sigma_{\mathcal{X}} : \mathcal{P} \mapsto \mathcal{P}$, which stores the new particles ordering used to reorder particles attributes. Permutations are represented by `IndexType` and stored in a vector container of size N_{alloc} , similarly to the points.

2.2.2. Particles with cell list representation

The neighbor search procedure uses a standard cell list approach. The implicit background grid with cell edge length r_c is employed to identify particle neighbors. To find the neighbors of particle i , the cell containing the particle is first determined (the cell is denoted by index c_i), and neighbors are searched only in adjacent cells.

To do that, particles are first assigned to cells. The procedure is described by Algorithm 1. First, for each particle, its cell index is computed and stored. Next the particles are sorted based on their cell index. Sorting particles by cell index c_i allows storing only the indices of the first and last particle for each cell.

The particles structure with cell list are implemented in `class ParticlesCellList`. In addition to base variables, particles with cell list includes an array \mathbf{c}_{idx} with size N_{alloc} to store cell index of each particle and an array \mathbf{i}_{fl} of pairs with size N_{cells} to store the index of the first and last particle in each cell.

The particle cell index is obtained by mapping n -dimensional particle coordinates to single number $c_i = g(\mathbf{x}_i)$. By default, standard *column/row-major order* indexing is used, but arbitrary mapping function can be defined. In three dimension, the cell index c_i is obtained as

$$c_i = [k_i, l_i, m_i] = \left(\left\lfloor \frac{x_i - x_{\mathcal{G},0}}{r_c} \right\rfloor, \left\lfloor \frac{y_i - y_{\mathcal{G},0}}{r_c} \right\rfloor, \left\lfloor \frac{z_i - z_{\mathcal{G},0}}{r_c} \right\rfloor \right) \quad (2)$$

$$c_i = k_i + l_i K_{\mathcal{G}} + m_i K_{\mathcal{G}} L_{\mathcal{G}} \quad (3)$$

where $K_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $L_{\mathcal{G}}$ represents dimensions of the domain grid $N_{\mathcal{G},dim} = [K_{\mathcal{G}}, L_{\mathcal{G}}, M_{\mathcal{G}}]$. The permutation of indexing (which index changes the slowest/fastest) is controlled by a template parameter of the indexer, similar to `TNL's`

NDArray. After computing cell indices, they are used to sort particles positions and attributes. Leveraging increasing GPU memory capacities, which are no longer a bottleneck for SPH simulations, swap arrays are used to avoid in-place reordering of particle attributes.

Once sorted, particles are assigned to cells by determining the first and last particle in each cell, a process known as *bucketing*. First, the array of pairs \mathbf{i}_{fl} is reset by filled with an invalid marker - upper limit of `IndexType` is used as the invalid marker. Since the particles are sorted, for every particle, its cell index c_i is compared with the previous c_{i-1} and next particle c_{i+1} . If $c_i \neq c_{i-1}$, particle i is the first particle in cell c_i because particle $i-1$ has already different cell index and $\mathbf{i}_{fl}[c_i].first = i$ is stored. On the contrary, if $c_i \neq c_{i+1}$, i is last particle in the cell c_i since the next one has already different cell index and we store $\mathbf{i}_{fl}[c_i].last = i$.

The `ParticlesCellList` class does not explicitly store the neighboring particles. For any particle or point $\mathbf{x} \in \bar{\Omega}$, a neighbor loop function (which is provided in two variants - both as a class method and a static function) iterates over all particles within the cutoff radius, as described in Algorithm 2. The interaction is defined by a lambda function passed as an argument to the neighbor loop.

2.2.3. Particles with Verlet list representation

For explicit neighbor storage, the class `ParticlesCellListWithList`, derived from class `ParticlesCellList`, which implements a cell list with list (Verlet list), is provided. It assumes each particle has at most $N_{nb,max}$ neighbors. In addition to variables defined by `ParticlesCellList`, this class defines a continuous array to store neighbors \mathbf{N}_{nb} . The neighbors are stored in so called *neighbor major* or *interleaved* order

$$\mathbf{N}_{nb}^{\text{GPU}} : \left[N_1, N_2, \dots, N_N, | \mathcal{N}_{1,1}, \mathcal{N}_{2,1}, \dots, \mathcal{N}_{N,1}, | \dots, | \mathcal{N}_{1,N_{nb,max}}, \mathcal{N}_{2,N_{nb,max}}, \dots, \mathcal{N}_{3,N_{nb,max}} \right] \quad (4)$$

where N_i denotes number of current neighbors of particle i and $\mathcal{N}_{i,j}$ denotes j -th neighbor of particle i . The array first stores neighbors counts N_i for all particles, followed by the first neighbors $\mathcal{N}_{i,1}$ for all particles and so on. The reason is that computing particle interactions in parallel involves each particle first loading the index of its first neighbor, then the index of its second neighbor, and so on. All the j -th neighbors of all particles are processed together, and the structure given by Eq. (4) allows the processed neighbor indices to be read as a continuous chunk of memory.

Using `ParticlesCellListWithList` with multiple particle sets, to distinguish and to be able to independently iterate over neighbors from different sets, each set has a unique label i_{set} . For example, with two particle sets \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} , neighbors from both sets follows structure Eq. (4) and are stored in consecutive order. For each particle i neighbor counts $N_i^{\mathcal{A}}$ from set \mathcal{A} are stored first, followed by neighbors $\mathcal{N}_{i,j}^{\mathcal{A}}$, then counts $N_i^{\mathcal{B}}$ and neighbors $\mathcal{N}_{i,j}^{\mathcal{B}}$.

For iteration over neighbors from set \mathcal{B} , the neighbor loop first reads $N_i^{\mathcal{A}}$, uses it to skip to $N_i^{\mathcal{B}}$, and iterates over the neighbors indices. This extends similarly to more than two particle sets, with $N_{nb,max}$ representing the total number of neighbors across all sets.

Algorithm 1 Assign particles to cells

Require:

- set \mathcal{P} of N_{tot} particles which involves vector of positions $\mathbf{x}[N_{\text{tot}}]$, fields with variables defined for particles $\{f_1[N_{\text{tot}}], f_2[N_{\text{tot}}], \dots, f_s[N_{\text{tot}}]\}$ and an array containing indices of cells where are particle located $\mathbf{c}_{\text{idx}}[N_{\text{tot}}]$, array to store permutations $\sigma[N_{\text{tot}}]$
- an array storing for each cell the first and last particle contained **firstLastPts** $[N_{\text{cells}}][2]$

For every particle, compute grid coordinates \mathbf{c}_i and use them to compute particle cell index using mapping function g .

```
for  $i \in \mathcal{P}$  do  
     $\mathbf{c}_i = (\mathbf{x}[i] - \mathbf{x}_{G,0})/r_c$   
     $\mathbf{c}_{\text{idx}}[i] = g(\mathbf{c}_i, \mathbf{N}_{G,n})$   
end for
```

Sort particles based on their cell index stored in \mathbf{c}_{idx} vector, build vector of permutations σ and reorder all the particles related filed based on new particle ordering stored in σ .

```
sortByKey( $\mathbf{c}_{\text{idx}}, \sigma$ )  
reorder( $\{\mathbf{x}, f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots, f_s\}, \sigma$ )
```

For every cell, store first and last particle contained inside.

```
for  $i \in \mathcal{P}$  do  
    if  $\mathbf{c}_{\text{idx}}[i] \neq \mathbf{c}_{\text{idx}}[i-1]$  then  
        # particle  $i$  is first particle in cell  $\mathbf{c}_{\text{idx}}[i]$   
         $\text{firstLastCellParticleList}[\mathbf{c}_{\text{idx}}[i]][0] = i$   
    end if  
    if  $\mathbf{c}_{\text{idx}}[i] \neq \mathbf{c}_{\text{idx}}[i+1]$  then  
        # particle  $i$  is last particle in cell  $\mathbf{c}_{\text{idx}}[i]$   
         $\text{firstLastCellParticleList}[\mathbf{c}_{\text{idx}}[i]][1] = i$   
    end if  
end for
```

Algorithm 2 Loop over neighbors for every particle - C27

Require:

- set \mathcal{P} of N_{tot} particles which involves vector of positions $\mathbf{x}[N_{\text{tot}}]$, fields with variables defined for particles $\{f_1[N_{\text{tot}}], f_2[N_{\text{tot}}], \dots, f_s[N_{\text{tot}}]\}$
- an array storing for each cell the first and last particle contained `firstLastPtcs` $[N_{\text{cells}}][2]$
- procedure (interaction) $\mathcal{F}(i, j)$ to perform pairwise between particles i and j

for $i \in \mathcal{P}$ **do***# For every entry particle or point compute grid coordinates $\mathbf{c}_i = [k, l, m]$.* $\mathbf{c}_i = (\mathbf{x}[i] - \mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{G},0})/r_c$ *# Loop over neighboring cells of particle i \mathbf{c}_i .***for** $m \in [m_i - 1, m_i + 1]$ **do****for** $l \in [l_i - 1, l_i + 1]$ **do****for** $k \in [k_i - 1, k_i + 1]$ **do***# Compute cell index c_j of current cell and load range of particle stored in that cell* $c_j = g([k, m, l], \mathbf{N}_{\mathcal{G},0})$ $j = \text{firstLastPtcs}[c_j][0]$ $j_{\text{end}} = \text{firstLastPtcs}[c_j][1]$ **if** $j_{\text{end}} > N_{\text{tot}}$ **then** $j_{\text{end}} = -1$ **end if***# Loop over particle in given cell and perform interaction $\mathcal{F}(i, j)$* **while** $j \geq j_{\text{end}}$ **do** $\mathcal{F}(i, j)$ **end while****end for****end for****end for****end for**

2.2.4. Particles class usage

The following code snippet provides a minimalistic example of looping over particles and, for each particle, iterating over its neighbors to sum their count. The lambda function `particleLoop` defines the operation performed for each particle and is passed to the `forall` function – either free function or member function (method), which wraps a parallel for loop. This method restricts the operation to particles within a given subdomain, ignoring overlaps in distributed computations, periodic boundaries, or subsets from specific algorithmic considerations. The second lambda function, `pairInteraction`, defines the operation performed for each neighbor and is passed as an argument to `neighborsLoop`, which is called by each particle within the `forall` loop.

Another argument of the neighbor search function is the `searchToken`, which provides metadata for the search function. This token is particularly useful when combining searches across multiple particle sets and defines in which set the neighbors loop iterate.

```
1 typename Particles::NeighborsLoopParams searchToken( particles ); //or
2 auto searchToken = particles->getSearchToken( particles );
3
4 const auto points_view = particles->getPoints().getConstView();
5 auto neighborsCounts_view = neighborsCounts.getView();
6
```

```

7 // Define operation performed for neighbor particle
8 auto pairInteraction = [=] __cuda_callable__ ( int i, int j, VectorType& r_i, int& nbsCount_i ) mutable
9 {
10 // Load position of neighboring particle and compare the distance
11 const VectorType r_j = points_view[ j ];
12 const VectorType r_ij = r_i - r_j;
13 const RealType drs = 12Norm( r_ij );
14 if( drs <= rCut ) {
15     *nbsCount_i += 1;
16 }
17 };
18
19 // Define operation which is performed for every particles
20 auto particleLoop = [=] __cuda_callable__ ( LocalIndexType i ) mutable
21 {
22     const VectorType r_i = points_view[ i ];
23     int nbsCount_i = 0;
24
25     ParticlesType::NeighborsLoop::exec( i, r_i, searchToken, pairInteraction, &nbsCount_i );
26
27     neighborsCounts_view[ i ] = nbsCount_i;
28 };
29 particles->forall( particleLoop );

```

2.2.5. Variable number of particles

For particle sets with a varying number of particles, we support both adding and removing particles from the domain. The particle set is allocated to accommodate N_{alloc} particles, with $N \leq N_{alloc}$ particles active. The allocated size N_{alloc} should be chosen to include sufficient reserve to minimize frequent reallocations. To add particles, new particles are placed in the array beyond the N active particles, and the active particle counter N is incremented.

To remove particles, a two-step procedure is followed. First, particles to be removed are marked as invalid by setting their position to upper limit of `RealType`, and the number of particles to be removed is counted. This count is stored in the particle base class as N_{del} . Second, during the neighbor search routine which involves sorting the particles based on their cell indices, the invalid particles are moved to the end of the arrays containing active particles. Once the sorting operation is complete, the active particle counter N is reduced by N_{del} .

2.2.6. Distributed particles system

The distributed implementation enables the use of multiple GPUs or nodes through the Message Passing Interface (MPI). We provide the class `DistributedParticles<ParticlesType>`, which wraps an instance of the specified particle class (defined by the template argument `ParticlesType`). This class manages the decomposition of the global domain into subdomains, communication between them, and balancing their sizes based on computational load.

The domain covered by the implicit uniform Cartesian grid $\mathcal{G}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{G},0}, N_{\mathcal{G},dim}, r_c)$, is divided along one, two, or three coordinate axes into blocks representing subdomains (squares in 2D, cuboids in 3D). The particles in the domain are split into local particle systems corresponding to individual subdomains. These subdomains are not uniform in size, the initial division ensures each subdomain contains approximately the same number of particles. As particle positions evolve, load balancing adjusts the size of individual blocks based on computation time or the number of particles in each block.

Each block is defined by its local grid $\mathcal{G}_{loc}(\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{G},0,loc}, N_{\mathcal{G},dim,loc}, r_c)$, and the cells of adjacent blocks are directly connected. The block dimensions $N_{\mathcal{G}}$ are extended in each direction by an overlap of width $w_{\mathcal{G}}$ expressed in number of grid cells (by default, $w_{\mathcal{G}} = 1$). The internal cells of a block corresponding to the overlap cells of adjacent blocks are tracked. During synchronization, particles in these overlap cells are collected and copied to send buffers. To enable collection and synchronization, particles must be assigned to cells, requiring the neighbor cell list to be updated before each synchronization.

Synchronization is performed in two steps. First, the number of particles to be sent and received is communicated. Next, particle values are exchanged: values from send buffers are sent to neighboring subdomains, and particles from neighboring subdomains are received, both using asynchronous MPI communication. Received particles are placed after the last active particle, and the particle count N for the given particle set is updated. After the synchronization, the neighbor search procedure needs to be called again to prepare the particle sets for the computation. With the

overlaps filled, the `forall` method loops only over the internal particles of the subdomain. When calling the neighbors loop for an internal particle, overlapping neighbors are automatically included in the computation.

During computation, the distributed particle class tracks the computation time t_{loc} and the number of particles N_{loc} for each subdomain. When the load balancing function is called, t_{loc} and N_{loc} are communicated. If the difference between neighboring subdomains exceeds a user-defined threshold, the domains are resized. During a single load balancing call, each subdomain can be enlarged or reduced by only one layer of cells. For one-dimensional decomposition, resizing is straightforward. Using two-dimensional decomposition, blocks are first balanced in one direction and then in the second dimension, strips of blocks are balanced to keep the block structure conforming. Similarly we balance three-dimensional domain decomposition.

2.3. Layer 3: Particles solver: Particle automaton

With the particle data structure available, the third layer builds on the shared properties of particle methods and the concept of unifying particle methods introduced earlier. This layer is used to construct a hydrodynamic solver, into which we integrate various SPH or GFDM schemes.

To connect particles defined in the second layer with variables carried by the particles, typically defined in the fourth layer, we introduce the class `ParticleSet<ParticleType, VariablesType, IntegratorVariablesType>`. This class takes as template arguments the type of particle representation (first argument) and a class defining the variables of the numerical model (second argument), and the time integration schemes (third argument). The variable classes must follow a specific template, providing all necessary methods to fit the `ParticleSet` class.

For SPH, we use a multi-set approach defined by the class `SolverMultisetHydro<Model>`. One particle set represents the fluid, while other sets represent boundary particles and additional particle groups, such as open boundary buffers. The solver is templated by the `Model` parameter, which is a class implementing specific numerical schemes, including their variables in a separate class. These variables are referenced by the `Model` class and provided to the solver's particle sets. This approach simplifies defining different variables for fluid, boundaries, and other particle sets (e.g., normal vectors for boundaries, which are typically not required for fluid particles).

In addition to storing the particle sets, the solver manages simulation control tasks, such as calling particle interaction functions, reading and writing particle data, and evaluating sensors and collecting measurement data. Functions defined by the solver are used to build the resulting applications. The resulting applications include a program main function, which creates instance of the solver and defines the simulation time loop. In the time loop, simulation functions are called, as discussed in detail later.

2.4. Layer 4: Particular numerical schemes

The fourth layer contains the variables and equations of the physical and numerical model itself. Different models are designed as individual classes derived from a shared template, which must provide the functions and structures expected by the target solver—in our case, the multi-set solver described in the previous layer 2.3. The solver takes the selected model as a template parameter `Model`.

For the multi-set solver targeting CFD problems, the model provides a structure with fluid variables, boundary variables, and open boundary variables (which can be omitted if the model does not include open boundaries). It also provides interaction functions between individual particle sets and a time integration scheme, including its variables. Thanks to the TNL data structures, all equations are written in a compact vector form, independent of dimensions, which significantly simplifies the notation. The clear correspondence between the code and the algebraic form of the equations is demonstrated by the snippet in Fig. 2, which implements the interaction between fluid particles in the δ -WCSPH scheme [34]

Figure 2: Correspondence between code and algebraic notation of the equations.

Some components, such as time integration schemes, are written using TNL’s expression templates, which further simplify implementation to resemble standard mathematical notation. For example, the popular Verlet time integration scheme [52] is implemented as follows

```

1 void
2 integrateStepVerlet()
3 {
4   // get variable views to avoid using the long access to variables in equations
5   auto r = fluid->getPoints().getView();
6   auto v = fluid->getVariables()->v.getView();
7   // ...rho, dvdt, drhodt, v_old, rho_old
8
9   r += v * dt + dvdt * ( 0.5 * dt * dt );
10  v_old += dvdt * ( dt * dt );
11  rho_old += drhodt * ( dt * dt );
12
13  v.swap( rho_old );
14  rho.swap( rho_old );
15 };

```

where each mathematical expression is compiled into a single parallel/GPU kernel based on the `Device` template parameter of the simulation.

To facilitate modification and extension of the implemented SPH variants, some parts of the schemes are designed as *plug-in patterns*. These include viscous terms, diffusive terms, equations of state, and pressure gradients, which are all building blocks that can be implemented separately as small functions. These functions can be directly plugged into the scheme through its configuration file, without needing to modify or access the model’s code itself.

A summary of all implemented *plug-in patterns* and numerical models is provided later in section 2.6, where we discuss in detail the features offered by TNL-SPH.

2.5. Resulting application

With all the structures described above, the last remaining part are the end-point applications that perform the simulations. In principle, these can be designed in an arbitrary manner based on the needs of a specific target. Here, we present the approach taken in the attached SPH examples, which serve both as demonstrations and regression tests.

Each of the attached examples, representing a complete application, consists of three parts: a compile-time configuration file `config.h`, a run-time configuration file `config.ini`, and the definition of the program and simulation main loop in `case.h`. As an example, we use the most canonical SPH test case, SPHERIC Test Case 2: a 3-dimensional dam break. In Appendix [Appendix A](#), we present the complete setup of this δ -WCSPH case without open boundaries, using the Verlet time integration scheme, including all configuration files.

The first configuration file, `config.h`, defines types, models, and model components specified at compile time. This includes the problem's dimension, the selection of the neighbor search algorithm, the numerical model, and its associated terms and algorithms. After modifying these parameters, the problem must be recompiled. The second configuration file, `config.ini`, specifies variables at run time. This includes paths to files with initial particle distributions, domain configuration details, the search radius r_c , and physical and numerical parameters of specific models (e.g., viscosity, speed of sound, etc.) or time-stepping settings. The final file, `case.h`, contains the main function of the program, where an instance of the selected solver is created and the simulation's time loop is defined.

Within the time loop, individual routines, such as *neighbors search* or *interaction*, are called according to the structure of the chosen time integration scheme. The primary purpose of this approach is to allow the time loop to be enhanced with custom user-defined functions, placed at arbitrary positions in the algorithm and tailored to specific needs, as we show in Appendix [Appendix A.1](#).

Once everything is set up, the resulting application must be compiled. Within TNL-SPH, this is achieved using a simple `CMakeLists.txt` file, which is part of the build `CMake` structure. For independent cases, we provide an example build using `cmake` with the `FetchContent` function, which automatically downloads TNL and TNL-SPH dependencies. To compile TNL-SPH applications, only standard compiler tools are required.

For more complex problems involving open boundaries or evaluation and control techniques, such as sensors to monitor variables at specific locations or interpolation planes, additional runtime configuration files are needed to set up these modules. For further details, refer to `TNL-SPH/examples` in the project repository [20] where we demonstrate examples of these features.

2.6. Implemented numerical schemes and features

TNL-SPH currently provides several SPH schemes with multiple formulations of boundary conditions, focusing on solving inviscid and viscous compressible, as well as nearly incompressible, barotropic isothermal flows, primarily using the weakly compressible fluid model. These formulations and schemes are organized into several *models*, as described in Section 2.4. TNL-SPH currently provides models `WCSPH-DBC`, which implements the δ -WCSPH formulation with multi-layer boundary conditions; `WCSPH-BI`, which includes the δ -WCSPH with boundary integrals and unconditionally stable SPH formulation proposed by Cercos-Pita et. al [9, 8]; and the `RSPH` model, which implements the Riemann-based δ -WCSPH. The design decision to split δ -WCSPH into several models based on shared properties aims to ensure clear and readable code without an overly complicated setup with too many possible variants.

In addition to models based on the weakly compressible fluid approach, we provide an implementation of the Symmetric Hyperbolic Thermodynamically Compatible (SHTC) equations [27] for a unified description of solids and fluids. The SHTC is implemented as a standalone *SHTC* model.

To summarize the key implemented features, we provide

- δ -WCSPH formulation including with various formulations of diffusive terms – Molteni formulation [34], Antuono formulation [1] and Fourtakas formulation [15]
- δ -WCSPH formulation with unconditionally stable SPH scheme proposed by Cercos-Pita et. al [9, 8]
- Riemann based WCSPH (RSPH) formulation following [54], including modified Roe solver [18]
- Various types of boundary conditions for solid walls: – dynamic boundary conditions (DBC) [11], modified dynamic boundary conditions (MDBC) [14], boundary integrals formulation (BI) [33] in its pure numerical form [7] and recent conservative formulation of boundary integrals (BI-Conservative) [8]

- Inlet and outlet boundary conditions [50, 49, 51] allowing to prescribe arbitrary Neumann or Dirichlet boundary conditions, periodic boundary conditions
- Several formulations of viscous term for both single layer and multi-layer boundary conditions – Morris formulation [37], Monaghan and Gingold formulation [35]
- Numerous time integration schemes: Verlet scheme [52], predictor-corrector Verlet scheme [30], Runge-Kutta 45 and implicit midpoint (IMP) integration scheme [9]
- Symmetric Hyperbolic Thermodynamically Compatible equations (SHTC) [27] for unifying description of solid and fluids

All these formulations can be utilized within the high-performance TNL-SPH framework.

Among the implemented schemes, we highlight the SHTC SPH scheme, which, to the authors' knowledge, is not implemented in any other HPC framework, and the WSPH-BI scheme, particularly its conservative formulation with implicit midpoint time integration [8], which is TNL-SPH's flagship solution for free surface flow.

In addition to the numerical schemes, the framework includes tools to analyze results and control simulations. The code provides sensors to evaluate desired variable values at specific points in the domain, interpolation planes or grids to interpolate particle data onto a structured grid or an unstructured mesh, and tools to evaluate results at particular sections. Tools to measure water levels or create surface representations of particles are also included. Functions for energy analysis [6, 8, 2] are also integrated into the solver.

To generate particles, an external preprocessing tool, *stl2particles* [29], based on *gmsk*, is provided. This tool can discretize external geometries (in .stl, .step, .igs, or any other format supported by *gmsk*) into a single layer of boundary elements. Multi-layer discretization of external geometries is not yet available, for these purposes, we recommend using *GenCase* by DualSPHysics [13].

3. Performance, validation, examples and usage

To evaluate performance, we first compare TNL-SPH with the main SPH codes supporting GPU computing. Additionally, we present results of strong and weak scaling using multiple GPUs. For the comparison, we use the standard *SPHERIC testcase 2*, 3-dimensional dam break, solved with the δ -WSPH scheme with Molteni diffusive term [34], artificial viscosity, [36] and Verlet scheme [52] with constant Δt . The setup files for all included solvers and scripts to benchmark all the solvers are provided in [17]. We used resolutions from interval $\Delta x \in [0.02, 0.006]$ m.

Figure 3 compares the average computation time per simulation step based on the number of particles for TNL-SPH, DualSPHysics [13], and OpenFPM [22]. The table 1 shows detail numbers for single resolution $\Delta x = 0.006$ m, including also *millions particles updated per second (MPUPS)*. All the codes uses exactly the same scheme, including boundary conditions and time integration. The results show that TNL-SPH is approximately 20% faster.

Figure 3: Comparing TNL-SPH with DualSPHysics and OpenFPM using δ -WSPH scheme, x-axis shows number of particles in millions, y-axis shows average computation time per one simulation step.

Table 1: *Spheric Test 02 - 3D dam break* is used, with $\Delta x = 0.006$ m, corresponding approximately to 4×10^6 particles. The data shows average computation time per simulation step and millions particles updates per second (MPUPS). Simulated physical time is 4 s.

GPU	TNL-SPH		DualSPHysics		OpenFPM	
	t_{step} [s]	MPUPS	t_{step} [s]	MPUPS	t_{step} [s]	MPUPS
A40	0.023	172.3	0.029	139.6	0.035	114.9
A100	0.024	170.2	0.027	148.2	0.028	143.4
H100	0.013	320.5	0.015	276.2		

Multi GPUs performance was tested with the same problem and schemes, using NVIDIA H100 cards. In the strong scaling test, a resolution of $\Delta x = 0.001$ m, corresponding to approximately 10^8 particles, was used.

In the weak scaling test, we used approximately 10^7 fluid particles per card. The total particle counts, logged in Table 3, vary slightly because the number of fluid particles scales with the power of three, while the number of boundary particles scales with the second power. Changes in resolution also slightly alter the overall dynamics, resulting in different numbers of fluid-boundary interactions, which marginally affect the results. The load per GPU is determined solely based on the fluid particle count as demonstrated in Fig. 4.

Table 2: Strong scaling in single precision using a single node with $8 \times$ Nvidia H100 GPUs. *Spheric Test 02 - 3D dam break* is used, with $\Delta x = 0.002$ m corresponding approximately to 10^8 particles. Simulated physical time is 4 s. GPUPS denotes billions of particles updates per second. Each MPI rank was mapped to its own GPU accelerator.

N_{GPUs}	GPUPS	t_{step} [s]	S_{speedup}	Eff
1	0.297	0.346	1.00	1.00
2	0.585	0.176	1.97	0.99
4	1.157	0.089	3.90	0.97
8	2.154	0.048	7.26	0.91

Table 3: Weak scaling in single precision using single node with $8 \times$ Nvidia H100 GPUs. *Spheric Test 02 - 3D dam break* is used, with $\Delta x = 0.004/\sqrt[3]{N}$ m corresponding approximately to range from 10^7 to 10^8 particles. Simulated physical time is 4 s. GPUPS denotes billions of particles updates per second. Each MPI rank was mapped to its own GPU accelerator.

N_{GPUs}	$N_{\text{ptcs}}(10^6)$	GPUPS	t_{step} [s]	S_{speedup}	Eff
1	15.2	0.335	0.045	1.00	1.00
2	28.5	0.622	0.046	1.98	0.99
4	53.8	1.147	0.047	3.87	0.97
8	102.8	2.136	0.048	7.54	0.94

The strong scaling results are presented in Tab. 2, achieving 91 % of parallel efficiency and the weak scaling results are shown in table Tab. 3 showing parallel efficiency 94 %.

Figure 4: Demonstration of the TNL-SPH multi-GPUs computations on the *Spheric Test 02 - 3D dam break* test case. First row shows velocity field, second row shows distribution of particles across GPUs (each color represents one GPU).

3.1. Validation on test cases

To demonstrate the accuracy of TNL-SPH, we present results for the 2-dimensional dam break test case [31] and the *SPHERIC test case 2*, a 3-dimensional dam break [23], using the stable configuration of the WCSPH-BI scheme. In both cases, we use an unconditionally stable scheme with a non-penetrable conservative formulation of the boundary integral [8], the implicit midpoint time integration scheme [9], the Monaghan-Gingold viscous term [35], and the diffusive term by Molteni [34]. For further details, see Appendix B. For the 2-dimensional case, we use an initial particle spacing of $\Delta x = 0.001$ m, smoothing length $h = 2\Delta x$, reference density $\rho_0 = 997$ kg·m⁻³, dynamic viscosity $\mu = 0.001$ Pa·s, speed of sound $c_s = 17.155$ m·s⁻¹, and artificial diffusion coefficient $\delta = 0.1$. The parameters of the implicit midpoint time integration are set based on [8]: maximum allowed number of subiterations $n_{maxiter} = 10$, residual tolerance $R_{\Delta t, tol}[E] = 2.64 \times 10^{-4}$, maximum allowed residual decay $g_R = 0.2$, relaxation coefficient increment $\Delta f = 0.25$, with CFL = 0.1. Time step is assumed constant, $\Delta t = CFL h/c_s^2$. In the 3-dimensional case, we use $\Delta x = 0.01$ m, $c_s = 45.17$ m·s⁻¹, and the implicit midpoint integration parameters are $n_{maxiter} = 30$, $R_{\Delta t, tol}[E] = 0.1$, maximum allowed residual decay $g_R = 0.5$, relaxation coefficient increment $\Delta f = 0.5$, with CFL = 0.1. The remaining parameters are the same as in the 2-dimensional case. The setup for both cases can be found in the project repository [20] at `tnl-sph/examples/WCSPH-BI/damBreak2D_WCSPH-BI` and `tnl-sph/examples/WCSPH-BI/damBreak3D_WCSPH-BI`. In the simulation, we evaluate the water level and pressure caused by the impact and compare them with experimental data. For detailed configuration of the positions of sensors for pressure and water level measurements, see [31] for the 2-dimensional dam break and [23] for the 3-dimensional dam break.

The pressure at point \mathbf{x} is evaluated as $p(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{j \in N_x(\mathcal{F})} p_j W_{ji} V_j / \gamma(\mathbf{x})$, where $\gamma(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{j \in N_x(\mathcal{F})} W_{ji} V_j$, p_j is the pressure at particle j , W_{ji} represents the weight function evaluated for the particle pair i, j , and V_j is the volume of particle j . To evaluate the water level at a point $\mathbf{x} = [x_0, y_0]$, assuming the water level changes along the z -axis (in the 3-dimensional case), we proceed from the bottom of the geometry (denoted z_0), moving in the z -direction by steps of Δx . At each point $\mathbf{x}_k = [x_0, y_0, z_0 + k\Delta x]$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$, we evaluate the normalized particle concentration $\gamma(\mathbf{x}_k)$. In the volume of the fluid, the support of the smoothing function is fully occupied by neighboring particles, resulting in $\gamma(\mathbf{x}_k) \simeq 1$. As the surface, we take points \mathbf{x}_k where $\gamma(\mathbf{x}_k) = 0.5$, which corresponds to approximately half-filling of the weight function support. The graphs Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 show instantaneous snapshots of pressure and water level obtained with a sampling interval of $\Delta t_{sensors} = 10^{-3}$ s, without any additional averaging or post-processing.

Figure 5: Results from 2D dam break test case. Comparison of pressure from sensors 2,3,5,8 (top row, from left to right) and water level from sensors (bottom row) with experimental data [31]. The black line shows the simulation results, blue line represents experimental measurements.

Figure 6: Results from Spheric Test 02 - 3D dam break test case. Comparison of pressure from sensors 2,3,5,8 (top row, from left to right) and water level from sensors (bottom row) with experimental data [23]. The black line shows the simulation results, blue line represents experimental measurements.

In the 2-dimensional case, there are certain deviations from the experimental data, particularly for the water levels. This may be because the experiment is not exactly two-dimensional. Another possible reason is that scattered fine particles may not be evaluated as part of the water level in some places, and to refine the results, it is necessary to adjust the method used to evaluate the water level. In the 3-dimensional case, there is excellent agreement between the simulation results and experimental data.

The dam break test cases, along with several other minimal examples (with open or periodic boundaries), are used as regression tests. For different configurations with various combinations of numerical terms and parameters, the tests compare accuracy against pre-computed values and evaluate computational times across different hardware. This ensures that changes made during continuous development do not affect the performance or accuracy of the code. A complete list of tests can be found in the project repository [20] at `tn1-sph/src/tools/configurationsToTest`.

3.2. Validation on real applications

To demonstrate TNL-SPH on industrial case, we simulated 15 seconds of physical time for the free surface flow in an open channel with a V-shaped overflow, as described in [45]. The simulation begins with an empty channel, incorporating the run-up state of filling. For the inlet, we prescribed a fixed flow rate of $Q = 11.4 \text{ l}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, using a constant velocity profile and a hydrostatic pressure profile. The hydrostatic pressure profile is updated based on the water level in the tank above the overflow. After approximately $t_{\text{phys.}} = 10$ seconds, the filling of the empty channel reaches a pseudo-stationary state, and the average water levels in the system stabilize. The water level in the outflow channel is set to $h_{\text{out}} = 0.095 \text{ m}$ using the outflow flood gate. For the downstream outlet boundary, zero gradients for velocity and pressure are prescribed. Inlet and outlet boundary conditions are implemented using multi-layer buffers. In the inlet buffer, particles are generated based on the minimal energy of the stable state, reducing spurious oscillations caused by the inlet.

As with the dam break cases above, we use the δ -WCSPH with conservative BI, implicit midpoint time integration, the Monaghan-Gingold viscous term, and the diffusive term by Molteni. The parameters are $\Delta x = 0.003 \text{ m}$, smoothing length $h = \sqrt{3}\Delta x$, reference density $\rho_0 = 1000 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, dynamic viscosity $\mu = 0.001 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$, speed of sound $c_s = 84 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, and artificial diffusion coefficient $\delta = 0.1$. Implicit midpoint scheme parameters are $n_{\text{maxiter}} = 30$, $R_{\Delta t, \text{tol.}}[E] = 0.02$, maximum allowed residual decay $g_R = 0.5$, relaxation coefficient increment $\Delta f = 0.5$, with CFL = 0.1 and variable time step. From the simulation, we evaluate the water level in several cross-sections of the channel and compare it with experimental data.

Figure 7 shows the results of the flow in the channel, demonstrating several representations of the results supported by TNL-SPH. Besides standard point clouds, where each particle is represented, a particle envelope representing the water level (or interface) can be obtained, as well as interpolation planes that interpolate the results in selected sections. The details of individual representations are shown in Fig. 7, where Fig. 9a depicts the particle representation, Fig. 9b shows the water level envelope representation, and the interpolation planes located at the central symmetry axis of the channel (Fig. 9d), at $y = -0.1 \text{ m}$ (Fig. 9c), and at $y = 0.1 \text{ m}$ (Fig. 9e)

Figure 7: Demonstration of different representations of results on V-shaped discharge object [45, 19]. The results show instantaneous snapshot of velocity field on the surface at $t = 10$ s. There is interpolation plane in the middle of the channel separating particle representation (*front*) and surface representation (*back*).

In Figure 8, we show a comparison of water levels obtained from the simulation with experimental data measured in [45]. The water level is evaluated at planes along the central axis of the channel located at the center ($y = 0$ m), at $y = 0.05$ m, $y = 0.1$ m, and at the wall of the channel at $y = 0.13$ m. The simulation results show very good agreement with the experimental measurements. As previously demonstrated in [19], the unconditionally stable scheme allows simulation of these problems without artificial viscosity or other artificial stabilizing techniques, significantly improving the nature of velocity fields in the channel.

Figure 8: Averaged water levels in the central plane of the channel $y = 0$ m and planes at $y = 0.05$ m, $y = 0.1$ and water level at the wall $y = 0.13$. Simulation data (*solid lines*) are compared experimental data (*filled circles with thin dashed line*) [45, 19].

Figure 9: Demonstration of different representations of results on V-shaped discharge object [45, 19]. The results show instantaneous snapshot of velocity field on the surface at $t = 10$ s. Fig. 9a shows particles representation of the fluid, Fig. 9b shows fluid envelope and Figs. 9c, 9d and 9e show results from interpolation planes located at the center of the channel at $y = -0.1$ m, $y = 0$ m and $y = 0.1$ m respectively.

4. Summary

In this paper, we presented TNL-SPH, a novel open-source implementation of the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method, designed as a submodule of the Template Numerical Library (TNL). TNL-SPH is tailored for hydrodynamic applications, leveraging weakly compressible formulations and modern C++ programming paradigms to deliver a high-performance, flexible, and portable framework for particle-based simulations. Its modular, four-layer design distinctly separates parallelism, particle data structures, simulation control, and numerical schemes, enabling – thanks to the TNL library – easy execution across various computing platforms, including multi-GPU and distributed systems, without requiring hardware-specific code modifications.

TNL-SPH distinguishes itself from existing SPH codes through its general particle framework, which supports not only SPH but also other short-range interaction particle methods, as aligned with the Unifying Mathematical Definition of Particle Methods by Pahlke [40]. This versatility is facilitated by a clear separation of numerical and performance-related code, unified neighbor search interfaces, and extensible simulation loops, allowing users to implement custom algorithms and schemes with ease, benefiting from the expression template and vector notation. The framework includes several advanced SPH schemes, such as the δ -WCSPH with conservative boundary integrals and implicit midpoint time integration which provides stable and very robust option for free surface flows, Riemann-based SPH, and the Symmetric Hyperbolic Thermodynamically Compatible (SHTC) model, alongside tools for result analysis, such as sensors, interpolation planes, and energy evaluation.

For the free surface flows TNL-SPH was validated both on standard test cases and industrial application. As the test case, we presented dam break problem, with excellent agreement in the 3-dimensional case. The industrial application of a V-shaped overflow channel further showcases TNL-SPH’s capability to handle complex free-surface flows, achieving very good agreement with experimental water level measurements. Performance benchmarks demonstrate that TNL-SPH outperforms comparable GPU-accelerated SPH codes by approximately 20% and exhibits strong and weak scaling efficiencies of 91% and 94%, respectively, on multi-GPU setups.

In summary, TNL-SPH offers a robust, high-performance, and user-friendly platform for hydrodynamic simulations, with a design that prioritizes flexibility, portability, and extensibility.

The code is open source, available at <https://gitlab.com/tnl-project/tnl-sph>. TNL-SPH is designed as *header only* which makes it simple to use. Future work will focus on implementing multi-resolution and adaptive particle refinement and enrichment of implemented schemes by the latest SPH advances, including multi-phase flows and also. In addition to numerical schemes, we plan further explore the algorithmic nature of cell lists themselves. The current drawback is that each particle needs to read data from too many neighbors in order to evaluate the interaction, which represents the most challenging acceleration bottleneck to remove.

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Appendix A. Example program configuration

The following snippets provide a setup for a δ -WCSPH problem with no open boundaries, integrated using the Verlet time integration scheme. The `config.h` file, containing compile-time parameters, and `case.h` defining the simulation algorithm, can be used for any problem of this type without changes. We demonstrate both files using *SPHERIC Test Case 2*: a 3-dimensional dam break, which can be found in the project repository [20] at `examples/WCSPH-DBC/damBreak3D_WCSPH-DBC`. The runtime parameters defined in `config.ini` are not presented here, but can be found at the same path.

Following snippet demonstrates the `config.h` file with compile-time parameters.

```
1 // file config.h
2
3 // device for which we compile the program
4 #include <TNL/Devices/Cuda.h>
5
6 using Device = TNL::Devices::Cuda;
7
8 // configuration of particles system
9 class ParticlesConfig
10 {
11     public:
12     using IndexType = int;
13     using CellIndexType = int;
14     using RealType = float;
15
16     static constexpr int spaceDimension = 3;
17
18     using UseWithDomainDecomposition = std::false_type;
19     using CellIndexerType = TNL::ParticleSystem::SimpleCellIndex< spaceDimension, std::index_sequence< 0, 1, 2 > >;
20 };
21
22 #include <TNL/Particles/ParticlesLinkedList.h>
23 using ParticlesType = TNL::ParticleSystem::ParticlesLinkedList< ParticlesConfig, Device >;
24
25 // basic SPH configuration
26 template< typename Device >
27 class SPHConfig
28 {
29     public:
30     using DeviceType = Device;
31
32     using IndexType = int;
33     using RealType = float;
34
35     static constexpr int spaceDimension = 3;
36 };
37
38 // configuration of selected SPH model
39 #include <SPH/Models/EquationOfState.h>
40 #include <SPH/Models/DiffusiveTerms.h>
41 #include <SPH/Models/ViscousTerms.h>
42 #include <SPH/Kernels.h>
43 #include <SPH/Models/WCSPH_DBC/BoundaryConditionsTypes.h>
44 #include <SPH/Models/WCSPH_DBC/IntegrationSchemes/VerletScheme.h>
45 #include <SPH/TimeStep.h>
46
47 class SPHParams
48 {
49     public:
50     using SPHConfig = SPHConfig< Device >;
51
52     using KernelFunction = TNL::SPH::KernelFunctions::WendlandKernel< SPHConfig >;
53     using DiffusiveTerm = TNL::SPH::DiffusiveTerms::MolteniDiffusiveTerm< SPHConfig >;
54     using ViscousTerm = TNL::SPH::ViscousTerms::ArtificialViscosity< SPHConfig >;
55     using EOS = TNL::SPH::EquationsOfState::TaitWeaklyCompressibleEOS< SPHConfig >;
56     using BCType = TNL::SPH::WCSPH_BCTypes::DBC;
57     using TimeStepping = TNL::SPH::ConstantTimeStep< SPHConfig >;
58     using IntegrationScheme = TNL::SPH::IntegrationSchemes::VerletScheme< SPHConfig >;
59 };
60
61 #include <SPH/Models/WCSPH_DBC/Interactions.h>
62 using Model = TNL::SPH::WCSPH_DBC< ParticlesSys, SPHParams< Device > >;
```

```

63
64 // simulation type
65 #include <SPH/SPHMultiset_CFD.h>
66 using Simulation = TNL::SPH::SPHMultiset_CFD< Model >;

```

First, we select the `Device` parameter, which defines the architecture for which the code is compiled. Next, `ParticlesConfig`, the configuration structure for the particle class, specifies data types, the problem's dimensionality, and whether a decomposed particle system is defined. Then, we define a similar configuration, `SPHConfig`, for the SPH model, specifying the dimensionality and data types. Next, `SPHParams` specifies predefined components of the selected SPH scheme (`Model`), which is plugged into the corresponding `Simulation` type.

In `case.h`, we have the main algorithm of the simulation

Main loop for WCSPH-BI scheme without open boundaries using Verlet time integration

1. Initialization: $\forall i \in \mathcal{P}_\Omega$, positions and initial conditions are loaded.
 2. Set $t = 0$.
 3. **While** $t < t_{\max}$:
 - 3.1. *Search for neighbors*: make all particle sets (\mathcal{F} , \mathcal{B}) searchable.
 - 3.2. *Perform interactions*: $\forall i \in \mathcal{P}_\Omega$ call \mathcal{F}_{init} , \mathcal{F} , \mathcal{F}_{fin} .
 - 3.3. *Integrate – Verlet step*: $\forall i \in \mathcal{P}_\Omega$ update variables.
 - 3.4. *Measure*: **If** $t \% \Delta t_{\text{measure}} = 0$: evaluate sensors and interpolation planes.
 - 3.5. *Save*: **If** $t \% \Delta t_{\text{save}} = 0$: save particle snapshot
 - 3.6. *Update time*: $t := t + \Delta t$.
-

which is represented by following code snippet

```

1 // file case.h
2
3 #include "template/config.h"
4
5 int main( int argc, char* argv[] )
6 {
7     Simulation sph;
8     sph.init( argc, argv );
9     sph.writeProlog();
10
11     while( sph.timeStepping.runTheSimulation() )
12     {
13         // search for neighbors
14         sph.performNeighborSearch();
15         // perform interaction with given model
16         sph.interact();
17         // in case of variable time step, compute the step
18         sph.computeTimeStep();
19         //integrate
20         sph.integrateVerletStep( SPHDefs::BCTYPE::integrateInTime() );
21         // check timers and if output should be performed, it is performed
22         sph.makeSnapshot();
23         // check timers and if measurement or interpolation should be performed, it is performed
24         sph.measure();
25         // update time step
26         sph.updateTime();
27     }
28
29     sph.writeEpilog();
30 }

```

Note that `ParticlesConfig`, `SPHConfig`, and `SPHDefs` can be used in their default variants or as modifications of their default templates.

```

1 // device for which we compile the program
2 #include <TNL/Devices/Cuda.h>
3 using Device = TNL::Devices::Cuda;
4
5 // type of particle representation and neighbor search algorithm
6 #include <TNL/Particles/ParticlesLinkedList.h>
7 using ParticlesType = TNL::ParticleSystem::ParticlesLinkedList< ParticlesConfigDefault, Device >;
8
9 // type of SPH model with default configuration
10 #include <SPH/Models/WCSPH_DBC/Interactions.h>
11 using Model = TNL::SPH::WCSPH_DBC< ParticlesType, SPHDefsDefault >;
12
13 // type of simulation
14 #include <SPH/SPHMultiset_CFD.h>
15 using Simulation = TNL::SPH::SPHMultiset_CFD< Model >;

```

Appendix A.1. Example with user defined function

The main purpose of this design of the main time loop is to allow adding custom functions at specific points in the SPH algorithm. For example, in a problem where we want to prescribe custom movement for the geometry and add additional smoothing of the density field, these functions can be implemented.

Main loop for WCSPH-BI scheme without open boundaries using Verlet time integration

1. Initialization: $\forall i \in \mathcal{P}_{\Omega}$, positions and initial conditions are loaded.
 2. Set $t = 0$.
 3. **While** $t < t_{\max}$:
 - 3.1. *Search for neighbors*: make all particle sets (\mathcal{F} , \mathcal{B}) searchable.
 - 3.2. *Perform interactions*: $\forall i \in \mathcal{P}_{\Omega}$ call $\mathcal{F}_{\text{init}}$, \mathcal{F} , \mathcal{F}_{fin} .
 - 3.3. **User defined function** – move boundary: $\forall i \in \mathcal{B}$ move as prescribed.
 - 3.4. *Integrate* – Verlet step: $\forall i \in \mathcal{P}_{\Omega}$ update variables.
 - 3.5. **User defined function** – filter density: $\forall i \in \mathcal{F}$ apply smoothing.
 - 3.6. *Measure*: **If** $t \% \Delta t_{\text{measure}} = 0$: evaluate sensors and interpolation planes.
 - 3.7. *Save*: **If** $t \% \Delta t_{\text{save}} = 0$: save particle snapshot
 - 3.8. *Update time*: $t := t + \Delta t$.
-

These functions can be coded separately, taking the particle sets as arguments, which provide all the particles and their variables, including functions to iterate through them.

```

1 // file case.h
2
3 #include "template/config.h"
4 #include "template/userCodedFunctions.h"
5
6 int main( int argc, char* argv[] )
7 {
8     Simulation sph;
9     sph.init( argc, argv );
10    sph.writeProlog();
11
12    while( sph.timeStepping.runTheSimulation() )
13    {
14        // search for neighbors
15        sph.performNeighborSearch();
16        // perform interaction with given model
17        sph.interact();
18        // USER CODED FUNCTION: move the geometry

```

```
19     userCodedFunctions::assignGeometryMovement( sph.boundary );
20     // integrate
21     sph.integrateVerletStep();
22     // USER CODED FUNCTIONS: smooth the density field
23     userCodedFunctions::filterDensityField( sph.fluid );
24     // output particle data
25     sph.makeSnapshot();
26     // check timers and if measurement or interpolation should be performed, is performed
27     sph.measure();
28     // update time step
29     sph.timeStepping.updateTimeStep();
30 }
31
32 sph.writeEpilog();
33 }
```

Appendix B. Description of WCSPH-BI model

WCSPH-BI is TNL-SPH's flagship solution for free surface flow problems. It is build using the standard WCSPH model but it includes the renormalization and natively incorporates boundary integral formulations of solid walls (BI). The WCSPH-BI model can solve three governing systems:

- An inviscid weakly compressible barotropic fluid in isothermal flow (Euler equations). The relation between density and pressure is given by the Cole equation of state.
- A viscous compressible Newtonian barotropic fluid in isothermal flow (Navier-Stokes equation for compressible fluid). The relation between density and pressure is given by the Cole equation of state.
- A viscous weakly compressible Newtonian barotropic fluid in isothermal flow (continuity equation for compressible flow with momentum conservation for inviscid fluid). The relation between density and pressure is given by the Cole equation of state.

Table B.4 summarize the particle variables defined for WCSPH-BI, including their type and software name. In addition to standard flow field variables, a renormalization factor γ of scalar type is used, which by default stores the Shepard factor of each particle. When higher-order normalization terms, such as the Libersky matrix, are employed, γ can be predefined as the required type. For boundary particles, their size S and boundary normal \mathbf{n} are included.

Table B.4: Variables of *Fluid* (\mathcal{F}) and *Boundary* (\mathcal{B}) particle sets in defined in WCSPH-BI model.

Field	Name	Type	Description	Units
Fluid particles (\mathcal{F})				
ρ	rho	ScalarArrayType	fluid density	kg·m ³
$D\rho/Dt$	drhodt	ScalarArrayType	time derivative of fluid density	kg·m ⁻³ ·s ⁻¹
p	p	ScalarArrayType	pressure (<i>this field is not actively used</i>)	Pa
\mathbf{v}	v	VectorArrayType	fluid/particle velocity	m·s ⁻¹
$D\mathbf{v}/Dt$	dvdt	VectorArrayType	time derivative of fluid velocity	m·s ⁻²
γ	gamma	ScalarArrayType	particle concentration (Shepard factor)	
Boundary particles (\mathcal{B})				
ρ	rho	ScalarArrayType	fluid density	kg·m ³
$D\rho/Dt$	drhodt	ScalarArrayType	time derivative of fluid density	kg·m ⁻³ ·s ⁻¹
p	p	ScalarArrayType	pressure (<i>this field is not actively used</i>)	Pa
\mathbf{v}	v	VectorArrayType	fluid/particle velocity	m·s ⁻¹
$D\mathbf{v}/Dt$	dvdt	VectorArrayType	time derivative of fluid velocity	m·s ⁻²
γ	gamma	ScalarArrayType	particle concentration (Shepard factor)	
\mathbf{n}	n	VectorArrayType	mnormal vector to boundary element	
S	elementSize	ScalarArrayType	length or area of boundary element	

Appendix B.1. Spatial discretization

Table B.5 provides a list of all spatial SPH discretizations, which are employed within the WCSPH-BI model. These discretizations are used to construct several built-in schemes of the model: the *Inviscid WCSPH-BI Consistent scheme*, the *Inviscid WCSPH-BI Conservative scheme*, the *Weakly Compressible WCSPH-BI Consistent scheme*, and the *Weakly Compressible WCSPH-BI Conservative scheme*, which in combination with implicit midpoint time integration (B.14) results in the **Unconditionally stable SPH algorithm** proposed by Cercos-Pita [8].

Table B.5: Description

Term	bulk discretization $\langle \bullet \rangle^\Omega$	boundary discretization $\langle \bullet \rangle^{\partial\Omega}$
$\langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \rangle$	$\langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \rangle_i^{\Omega, \text{asym.}} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{F}} (\mathbf{v}_j - \mathbf{v}_i) \nabla_i W_{ij}^{\mathcal{L}} V_j$	$\langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \rangle_i^{\partial\Omega, \text{asym.}} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{B}} (\mathbf{v}_j - \mathbf{v}_i) \mathbf{n}_j W_{ij}^{\mathcal{L}} S_j$
		$\langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \rangle_i^{\partial\Omega, \text{conserv.}} = 2 \sum_{j \in \mathcal{B}} (\mathbf{v}_j - \mathbf{v}_i) \mathbf{n}_j W_{ij} S_j$
$\langle \nabla p \rangle$	$\langle \nabla p \rangle^{\Omega, \text{sym.}} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{F}} (p_i + p_j) \nabla_i W_{ij}^{\mathcal{L}} V_j$	$\langle \nabla p \rangle^{\partial\Omega, \text{sym.}} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{B}} (p_i + p_j) \mathbf{n}_j W_{ij}^{\mathcal{L}} S_j$
		$\langle \nabla p \rangle_i^{\partial\Omega, \text{conserv.}} = 2p_i \sum_{j \in \mathcal{B}} \mathbf{n}_j W_{ij} S_j.$
$\langle \Delta \mathbf{v} \rangle$	$\langle \Delta \mathbf{v} \rangle_{i, \text{MVT}}^\Omega = 2 \sum_{j \in \mathcal{F}} (\mathbf{v}_i - \mathbf{v}_j) \frac{(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij}}{\ (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j)\ ^2} V_j$	$\langle \Delta \mathbf{v} \rangle_{i, \text{MVT}}^{\partial\Omega} = 2 \sum_{j \in \mathcal{B}} \frac{(\mathbf{v}_i - \mathbf{v}_j)}{(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j) \cdot \mathbf{n}_j} W_{ji} S_j$
$\langle \Delta \mathbf{v} + 2\nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) \rangle$	$\langle \Delta \mathbf{v} + 2\nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) \rangle_{i, \text{MGVT}}^\Omega = 2(n+2)\mu \sum_{j \in \mathcal{F}} \frac{(\mathbf{v}_i - \mathbf{v}_j) \cdot (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j)}{\ (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j)\ ^2} \nabla_i W_{ij}^{\mathcal{L}} V_j$	$\langle \Delta \mathbf{v} + 2\nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) \rangle_{i, \text{MGVT}}^{\partial\Omega} = 2(n+2) \sum_{j \in \mathcal{B}} \frac{(\mathbf{v}_i - \mathbf{v}_j)}{(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j) \cdot \mathbf{n}_j} W_{ij}^{\mathcal{L}} S_j.$

The spatial WCSPH-BI schemes include, by default, two additional algorithms inspired by [7]. The first is the *Conservative Velocity-Based Elastic Bounce* (EB-Conservative) 6, which enforces the non-penetrability of solid walls. Alternatively, the simple *Elastic Bounce* (EB- ε) algorithm, which allows the determination of the relative energy of reflection (controlled by $\varepsilon \in [0, 1]$), can be used. The second is the *Near-Boundary Particle Shifting* (NVBC-PST), which adjusts the positions of particles near the boundary to ensure that particles are not too close to the boundary and that their geometrical volume does not exceed the walls.

Inviscid WCSPH-BI Conservative

$$\frac{D\mathbf{x}_i(t)}{Dt} = \mathbf{v}_i(t) \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$$\left\langle \frac{D\rho}{Dt} \right\rangle_i(t) = -\rho_i \langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \rangle_i(t) + \delta_\psi h c_0 \mathcal{D}_i(t) \quad (\text{B.2})$$

$$\left\langle \frac{D\mathbf{v}}{Dt} \right\rangle_i(t) = -\frac{1}{\rho_i(t)} \langle \nabla p \rangle_i(t) - \mathbf{g} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

$$p_i(t) = p_0 + c_0^2(\rho_i(t) - \rho_0) \quad (\text{B.4})$$

- $\langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \rangle_i = \langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \rangle_i^{\Omega, \text{asym.}} + \langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \rangle_i^{\partial\Omega, \text{conserv.}}$
- $\langle \nabla p \rangle_i = \langle \nabla p \rangle_i^{\Omega, \text{sym.}} + \langle \nabla p \rangle_i^{\partial\Omega, \text{conserv.}}$
- optional diffusive term \mathcal{D}_i
- conservative elastic bounce (EB-Conservative), Algorithm 6
- near boundary volume shifting correction (NBVC-PST), Algorithm 7

Table B.6: Conservative WCSPH-BI spatial scheme for (weakly) compressible inviscid fluid barotropic fluid in isothermal flow (Euler equations).

Weakly compressible: WCSPH-BI Conservative

$$\frac{D\mathbf{x}_i(t)}{Dt} = \mathbf{v}_i(t) \quad (\text{B.5})$$

$$\left\langle \frac{D\rho}{Dt} \right\rangle_i(t) = -\rho_i \langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \rangle_i(t) + \delta_\psi h c_0 \mathcal{D}_i(t) \quad (\text{B.6})$$

$$\left\langle \frac{D\mathbf{v}}{Dt} \right\rangle_i(t) = -\frac{1}{\rho_i(t)} \langle \nabla p \rangle_i(t) + \mu \langle \Delta \mathbf{v} + 2\nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) \rangle_i(t) - \mathbf{g} \quad (\text{B.7})$$

$$p_i(t) = p_0 + c_0^2(\rho_i(t) - \rho_0) \quad (\text{B.8})$$

- $\langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \rangle_i = \langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \rangle_i^{\Omega, \text{asym.}} + \langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \rangle_i^{\partial\Omega, \text{conserv.}}$
- $\langle \nabla p \rangle_i = \langle \nabla p \rangle_i^{\Omega, \text{sym.}} + \langle \nabla p \rangle_i^{\partial\Omega, \text{conserv.}}$
- $\langle \Delta \mathbf{v} + 2\nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) \rangle = \langle \Delta \mathbf{v} + 2\nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) \rangle^{\Omega, \text{MG}} + \langle \Delta \mathbf{v} + 2\nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) \rangle^{\partial\Omega, \text{MG, no-slip}}$
- optional diffusive term \mathcal{D}_i
- conservative elastic bounce (EB-Conservative), Algorithm 6
- near boundary volume shifting correction (NBVC-PST), Algorithm 7

Table B.7: Conservative WCSPH-BI spatial scheme for (weakly) compressible Newtonian barotropic fluid in isothermal flow (Navier-Stokes equations).

To integrate the equations in time, WCSPH-BI provides the following time integration schemes. We would like to highlight again the implicit midpoint scheme, which, in contrast to widely used explicit schemes, offers superior stability improvements.

Weakly compressible WCSPPH-BI Consistent

$$\frac{D\mathbf{x}_i(t)}{Dt} = \mathbf{v}_i(t) \quad (\text{B.9})$$

$$\langle \gamma \rangle_i(t) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{F}} W_{ij} V_j \quad (\text{B.10})$$

$$\left\langle \frac{D\rho}{Dt} \right\rangle_i(t) = \frac{1}{\langle \gamma \rangle_i(t)} \left(-\rho_i \langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \rangle_i(t) + \delta_\psi h c_0 \mathcal{D}_i(t) \right) \quad (\text{B.11})$$

$$\left\langle \frac{D\mathbf{v}}{Dt} \right\rangle_i(t) = \frac{1}{\langle \gamma \rangle_i(t)} \left(-\frac{1}{\rho_i(t)} \langle \nabla p \rangle_i(t) + \mu \langle \Delta \mathbf{v} + 2\nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) \rangle_i(t) \right) - \mathbf{g} \quad (\text{B.12})$$

$$p_i(t) = p_0 + c_0^2(\rho_i(t) - \rho_0) \quad (\text{B.13})$$

- $\langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \rangle_i = \langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \rangle_i^{\Omega, \text{asym.}} + \langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \rangle_i^{\partial\Omega, \text{asym.}}$
- $\langle \nabla p \rangle_i = \langle \nabla p \rangle_i^{\Omega, \text{sym.}} + \langle \nabla p \rangle_i^{\partial\Omega, \text{sym.}}$
- $\langle \Delta \mathbf{v} + 2\nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) \rangle = \langle \Delta \mathbf{v} + 2\nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) \rangle^{\Omega, \text{MG}} + \langle \Delta \mathbf{v} + 2\nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) \rangle^{\partial\Omega, \text{MG, no-slip}}$
- optional diffusive term \mathcal{D}_i
- conservative elastic bounce (EB-Conservative), Algorithm 6
- near boundary volume shifting correction (NBVC-PST), Algorithm 7

Table B.8: Consistent WCSPPH-BI spatial scheme for (weakly) compressible Newtonian barotropic fluid in isothermal flow (Navier-Stokes equations).

Appendix B.2. Integration in time - Implicit mid-point scheme (IMP)

To compute the time derivatives at $t_{n+1/2}$, the implicit midpoint scheme includes an inner iteration loop, denoted by the superscript m .

$$\hat{\rho}_i^m(t_{n+1/2}) = \rho_i^n + \frac{\Delta t}{2} \tilde{\rho}_i^m, \quad (\text{B.14a})$$

$$\tilde{\rho}_i^{m+1} = f^m \left\langle \frac{D\rho}{Dt} \right\rangle_i(t_{n+1/2}) + (1 - f^m) \tilde{\rho}_i^m \quad (\text{B.14b})$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{v}}_i^m(t_{n+1/2}) = \mathbf{v}_i^n + \frac{\Delta t}{2} \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_i^m, \quad (\text{B.14c})$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{v}}_i^{m+1} = f^m \left\langle \frac{D\mathbf{v}}{Dt} \right\rangle_i(t_{n+1/2}) + (1 - f^m) \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_i^m \quad (\text{B.14d})$$

where $f^m \in [0, 1]$ is relaxation. The iteration is controlled by residuals of the energy conservation

$$R_{\Delta t} [E](t) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{F}} \left| m \mathbf{v}_j(t) \cdot \left\langle \frac{D\mathbf{v}}{Dt} \right\rangle_j(t) \right| + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{F}} \left| \frac{m p_j(t)}{\rho_j^2(t)} \left\langle \frac{D\rho}{Dt} \right\rangle_j(t) \right|. \quad (\text{B.14e})$$

At the first step of the inner iteration loop, relaxation is not considered. The relaxation factor is progressively increased as $f^{m+1} = \Delta f + (1 - \Delta f) f^m$ if the residuals do not decrease at a given geometrical rate r_R (i.e., if $r_R > (R_{\Delta t}^m [E] / R_{\Delta t}^{m-1} [E])$). Both Δf and r_R are tunable parameters.

Appendix B.3. Integration in time - Verlet scheme

$$\mathbf{r}_i(t_{n+1}) = \mathbf{r}_i(t_{n-1}) + \Delta t \mathbf{v}_i(t_n) + \frac{1}{2} \Delta t^2 \left\langle \frac{D\mathbf{v}}{Dt} \right\rangle_i(t_n) \quad (\text{B.15a})$$

$$\mathbf{v}_i(t_{n+1}) = \mathbf{v}_i(t_{n-1}) + 2\Delta t \left\langle \frac{D\mathbf{v}}{Dt} \right\rangle_i(t_n) \quad (\text{B.15b})$$

$$\rho_i(t_{n+1}) = \rho_i(t_{n-1}) + 2\Delta t \left\langle \frac{D\rho}{Dt} \right\rangle_i(t_n) \quad (\text{B.15c})$$

Due to integration over staggered intervals, the system is decoupled, which can lead to instability [13]. To stabilize the scheme, an intermediate step is performed every f_{ES} -th step (with a default $f_{ES} = 40$) using a first-order explicit Euler scheme.

$$\mathbf{r}_i(t_{n+1}) = \mathbf{r}_i(t_{n-1}) + \Delta t \mathbf{v}_i(t_n) + \frac{1}{2} \Delta t^2 \left\langle \frac{D\mathbf{v}}{Dt} \right\rangle_i(t_n) \quad (\text{B.16a})$$

$$\mathbf{v}_i(t_{n+1}) = \mathbf{v}_i(t_n) + \Delta t \left\langle \frac{D\mathbf{v}}{Dt} \right\rangle_i(t_n) \quad (\text{B.16b})$$

$$\rho_i(t_{n+1}) = \rho_i(t_n) + \Delta t \left\langle \frac{D\rho}{Dt} \right\rangle_i(t_n). \quad (\text{B.16c})$$

Appendix B.4. Integration in time - Symplectic Verlet scheme

The symplectic position Verlet method [30] is a two-stage predictor-corrector time integration scheme. In principle, it is time-reversible and preserves the geometric structure when applied to a suitable system, which is not the case for SPH with explicitly computed density [26]. The corrector follows the approach used in [42].

Predictor:

$$\mathbf{r}_i(t_{n+1/2}) = \mathbf{r}_i(t_n) + \frac{1}{2} \Delta t \mathbf{v}_i(t_n) \quad (\text{B.17a})$$

$$\mathbf{v}_i(t_{n+1/2}) = \mathbf{v}_i(t_n) + \frac{1}{2} \Delta t \left\langle \frac{D\mathbf{v}}{Dt} \right\rangle_i(t_n) \quad (\text{B.17b})$$

$$\rho_i(t_{n+1/2}) = \rho_i(t_n) + \frac{1}{2} \Delta t \left\langle \frac{D\rho}{Dt} \right\rangle_i(t_n) \quad (\text{B.17c})$$

$$(\text{B.17d})$$

Corrector:

$$\mathbf{r}_i(t_{n+1}) = \mathbf{r}_i(t_{n-1}) + \Delta t \frac{(\mathbf{v}_i(t_n) + \mathbf{v}_i(t_{n+1}))}{2} \quad (\text{B.18})$$

$$\mathbf{v}_i(t_{n+1}) = \mathbf{v}_i(t_n) + \Delta t \left\langle \frac{D\mathbf{v}}{Dt} \right\rangle_i(t_{n+1/2}) \quad (\text{B.19})$$

$$\rho_i(t_{n+1}) = \rho_i(t_n) + \frac{2 - \epsilon}{2 + \epsilon} \rho_i(t_{n+1/2}), \quad \epsilon = -\Delta t \frac{1}{\rho_i(t_{n+1/2})} \left\langle \frac{D\rho}{Dt} \right\rangle_i(t_{n+1/2}) \quad (\text{B.20})$$

Appendix B.5. Interaction functions

WCSPH-BI is designed as model for multi-set SPH solver, requiring three interaction functions. The *initialize interaction* function $\mathcal{F}_{\text{initialize}}$ precomputes variables required for the interaction, if necessary. The main *interact* function \mathcal{F} handles the core interaction. The *finalize interaction* function $\mathcal{F}_{\text{finalize}}$ performs post-interaction routines.

Algorithm 3 Initialize interaction $\mathcal{F}_{\text{initialize}}$:

empty function

Algorithm 4 Interact \mathcal{F} :

1. Loop over boundary particles: $\forall i \in \mathcal{B}$ do (*skipped if not required by selected scheme*):
 - Loop over fluid neighbors: $\forall j \in \mathcal{N}_i(\mathcal{F})$ compute contribution to ρ_i
 2. Loop over fluid particles: $\forall i \in \mathcal{F}$ do
 - Loop over fluid neighbors: $\forall j \in \mathcal{N}_i(\mathcal{F})$ compute contribution to $\langle D\rho/Dt \rangle_i$, $\langle D\mathbf{u}/Dt \rangle_i$ and $\langle \gamma \rangle_i$
 - Loop over boundary neighbors: $\forall j \in \mathcal{N}_i(\mathcal{B})$ compute contribution to $\langle D\rho/Dt \rangle_i$ and $\langle D\mathbf{u}/Dt \rangle_i$
-

Algorithm 5 Finalize interaction $\mathcal{F}_{finalize}$:

- Loop over fluid particles: $\forall i \in \mathcal{F}$ do
- Loop over fluid neighbors: $\forall j \in \mathcal{N}_i(\mathcal{F})$ compute contribution to ρ_i
2. Loop over fluid particles: $\forall i \in \mathcal{F}$ do
 - normalize derivatives $\langle D\rho/Dt \rangle_i$ and $\langle D\mathbf{u}/Dt \rangle_i$ with $\langle \gamma \rangle_i$
 - add acceleration by external forces \mathbf{f}_i
-

Algorithm 6 Conservative, velocity elastic bounce (EB-Conservative)

Require:

- set of fluid particles \mathcal{F} , set of boundary particles (elements) \mathcal{B}
- initial particle distance Δx , coefficient for activation distance of the bounce h_{fac} in normal direction (activation distance in normal direction is given as $h_{fac}\Delta x$), coefficient for activation distance of the bounce r_{box} in tangetial direction (activation distance in tangetial direction is given as $r_{box}S_j^{1/(d-1)}$),

for $i \in \mathcal{F}$ **do****for** $j \in \mathcal{N}_i \subseteq \mathcal{B}$ **do**

$$x_n = (\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i) \cdot \mathbf{n}_j$$

*# Particle is already behind the wall.***if** $x_n < 0$ **then** return**end if**

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \mathbf{x}_{ji} - x_n \mathbf{n}_j$$

*# Particle is too far from boundary node j***if** $\|\mathbf{x}_t\| > r_{box}S_j^{1/(d-1)}$ **then** return**end if**

$$v_n = \Delta t (\mathbf{v}_i \cdot \mathbf{n}_j)$$

*# Particle is already running from the boundary.***if** $r_n < 0$ **then** return**end if***# Reflect the particle.***if** $r_n - v_n < h_{fac}\Delta x$ **then**

$$\mathbf{v}_{mov} = \mathbf{v}_i + \Delta t \left(\frac{D\mathbf{v}_i}{Dt} \right)_{mod}$$

$$\mathbf{v}_{bounc} = \mathbf{v}_{\Delta t} - 2(\mathbf{v}_{mov} \cdot \mathbf{n}_j) \mathbf{n}_j$$

$$\left(\frac{D\mathbf{v}_i}{Dt} \right)_{mod} = \frac{\mathbf{v}_{bounc} - \mathbf{v}_i}{\Delta t}$$

$$\mathbf{v}_{i,mod} = \mathbf{v}_i + \frac{\Delta t}{2} \left(\frac{D\mathbf{v}_i}{Dt} \right)_{mod}$$

end if**end for**

$$\left(\frac{D\mathbf{v}_i}{Dt} \right) = \left(\frac{D\mathbf{v}_i}{Dt} \right)_{mod}$$

end for

Algorithm 7 Near-boundary particle shifting

Require:

- set of fluid particles \mathcal{F} , set of boundary particles (elements) \mathcal{B}
- initial particle distance Δx , coefficient for activation distance of the bounce h_{fac} in normal direction (activation distance in normal direction is given as $h_{fac}\Delta x$), coefficient for activation distance of the bounce r_{box} in tangetial direction (activation distance in tangetial direction is given as $r_{box}S_j^{1/(d-1)}$),

```
for  $i \in \mathcal{F}$  do  
  # Compute minial distance of particle from boundary  
   $R_i = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt[d]{\frac{m}{\rho_i}}$   
  for  $j \in \mathcal{N}_i \subseteq \mathcal{B}$  do  
     $x_n = (\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i) \cdot \mathbf{n}_j$   
  
    # Particle is too far from boundary or it is in right distance.  
    if  $x_n > R_i$  then return  
    end if  
  
     $\mathbf{x}_t = \mathbf{x}_{ji} - x_n \mathbf{n}_j$   
  
    # Particle is too far from boundary node j  
    if  $\|\mathbf{x}_t\| > r_{box} \sqrt[d-1]{S_j}$  then return  
    end if  
  
     $\mathbf{x}_i = \mathbf{x}_i + (x_n - R_i) \mathbf{n}_j$   
  end for  
end for
```

Appendix B.6. Model parameters

To configure and tune the WCSPH-BI model, tables B.10 and B.9 list all available parameters. Table B.9 provides all parameters required by the model, which can be specified at runtime. These include domain size, names of particle input files, time-stepping information, and parameters for individual terms and algorithms. Table B.10 lists compile-time *plug-in* parameters, specified in `ModelConfig`.

Table B.9: Parameters of WCSPH-BI model, provided in runtime.

Var	Variable Name	Type	Commentary	Default Value
Δx	dp	RealType	initial particle distance [m]	0.f
h	h	RealType	smoothing length [m]	0.f
r_{cut}	searchRadius	RealType	radius of kernel support [m]	0.f
$m_{\mathcal{F}}$	mass	RealType	particle mass [kg]	0.f
$m_{\mathcal{B}}$	massBoundary	RealType	boundary particle mass [kg]	0.f
S	boundaryElementSize	RealType	size of boundary element [m]	0.f
δ	delta	RealType	coefficient of diffusive term (DT) [-]	0.1f
α	alpha	RealType	parameter of artificial viscosity [-]	0.02f
μ	dynamicViscosity	RealType	value of dynamic viscosity [Pa/s]	0.f
	scaleBVTCoef	RealType	coefficient used to tune BVT effect to physical behavior [-]	1.f
C_s	speedOfSound	RealType	numerical speed of sound used in SPH calculations [m/s]	0.f
	coefB	RealType	coefficient of the Tait equation of state	0.f
ρ_0	rho0	RealType	referential density of the fluid [kg/m ³]	0.f
ε	enableElasticBounce	bool	enable elastic bounce boundary correction	true
	elasticFactor	RealType	elastic boundary correction factor	1.f
	r_boxFactor	RealType	r_box = r_boxFactor * dp	1.5f
	minimalDistanceFactor	RealType	minimal distance factor	0.5f
	dtInit	RealType	initial time step [s]	0.f
	cfl	RealType	CFL number [-]	0.f
	dtMin	RealType	minimal allowed time step [s]	0.f
	midpointMaxIterations	int	max number of midpoint iterations [-]	50
	midpointResidualTolerance	RealType	midpoint iteration tolerance to reach [-]	1.e-7
	midpointRelaxCoef	RealType	midpoint relaxation coefficient [-]	0
	midpointRelaxCoef_0	RealType	midpoint relaxation coefficient in first iteration [-]	0
	midpointResidualMinimalDecay	RealType	midpoint minimal decay of residual [-]	0.2f
	midpointRelaxCoefIncrement	RealType	midpoint increment of relaxation coefficient [-]	0
	gravity	VectorType	external forces [m ² /s]	0.f
	eps	RealType	constant to prevent zero in denominator [-]	0.001f

Table B.10: Modular *plug-in* terms provided in WCSPH-BI model and their implemented variants.

Parameter	Option	Description
KernelFunction	WendlandKernel	Wendland C2 kernel [53]
DiffusiveTerm	None	
	MolteniDiffusiveTerm	Diffusive term proposed by Molteni [34]
	FourtakasDiffusiveTerm	Diffusive term proposed by Fourtakas [15]
ViscousTerm	None	
	ArtificialViscosity	Artificial viscosity [36]
	PhysicalViscosity_MVT	Morris viscous term [37]
	PhysicalViscosity_MGVT	Monaghan & Gingold viscous term [35]
EOS	ColeEquationOfState	Weakly compressible Cole EOS [10]
	LinearizedColeEquationOfState	Linearized weakly compressible Cole EOS
BCType	BIConservative_numeric	Conservative formulation of boundary integrals [8]
	BIConsistent_numeric	Numeric renormalized formulation of boundary integrals [7]
TimeStepping	ConstantTimeStep	
	VariableTimeStep	
IntegrationScheme	MidpointScheme	Implicit midpoint scheme [9, 8]
	VerletScheme	Verlet scheme [52]
	SymplecticVerletScheme	Symplectic Verlet Scheme [30]
	RK45	Runge Kutta 4(5) scheme [48]

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